

Studies of Vanadyl Complexes of Phthalic Acid and Substituted Phthalic Acids

N. G. PALASKAR

Department of Chemistry, S. B. E. S. College of Science, Aurangabad—431 001

Manuscript received 23 August 1976; revised 1 June 1977; accepted 3 October 1977

The interactions of vanadyl ion with phthalic acid and 3-chloro, 3-bromo, 3-iodo, 3-nitro, 4-nitro and 3,6-dichlorophthalic acids have been investigated by Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti at 30° and $\mu=0.1 M$ NaClO₄ in aqueous medium. The linear relation between metal-ligand stability constants and proton-ligand stability constants was critically examined for complexes of vanadyl ion.

VANADYL complexes of acetylacetone¹, 3-hydroxyquinoline², N,N'-dihydroxy-EDTA³, 1,10-phenanthroline⁴, tiron(2,4-dihydroxybenzene-1,3-disulphonic acid⁵), *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime⁶, etc., have been reported in the literature. The present work deals with a systematic study of stability constants of complexes of some substituted phthalic acids with vanadyl ion in aqueous medium of 0.1 M (NaClO₄). This is a continuation of the earlier work on uranyl chelates of phthalic acids⁵.

Experimental

Chemicals: Phthalic acid, sodium hydroxide, sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid were obtained from E. Meck. 3-nitrophthalic acid, 4-nitrophthalic acid and 3,6-dichlorophthalic acid were procured from British Drug House, India. 3-chlorophthalic acid, 3-bromophthalic acid and 3-iodophthalic acid were prepared by standard method. All solutions were prepared by using double distilled carbon dioxide free water.

Metal salt solution: Vanadyl sulphate of AnalaR (BDH) quality was used and Vo(OH)₂ was precipitated by the addition of sodium hydroxide solution. The vanadyl hydroxide was washed free from the sulphate ion and was then dissolved in perchloric acid to obtain a stable vanadyl perchlorate solution.

pH-meter: Beckman model H-2 pH-meter, in conjunction with Beckman standard general purpose glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode, was used for the potentiometric titrations. The measurements could be made with an accuracy of ± 0.02 pH unit and the reproducibility of the readings was of the same order. The pH-meter was calibrated using Cambridge buffer tablets of pH 4.01 and 9.11. The temperature of the solutions in the titration vessel was maintained at 30° with a thermostatic arrangement.

Calvin-Bjerrum titration: The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration of solutions of (i) free HClO₄, (ii) free HClO₄+reagent, (iii) free HClO₄+reagent+vanadyl ion and (iv) free HClO₄+vanadyl ion against standard NaOH solution added from microburette giving an accuracy of 0.025 ml. The ionic strength of the solution for each set was maintained at 0.1 M by the addition of appropriate quantity of NaClO₄ solution. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen-free nitrogen gas through an assembly containing the electrodes, to keep away CO₂.

Results and Discussion

Irving and Rossotti expression⁷ was used for the calculations of \bar{n} values⁸ which were used for the determination of stability constants of vanadyl complexes. Factors like hydrolysis of vanadyl ion, presence of polynuclear hydrogen and hydroxyl ions was assumed absent. The assumptions were justified on the following grounds:

- (i) The departure of the metal complex titration curve from the reagent curve commences from about pH 2.4 which is less than the pH of hydrolysis of metal ion. The variation of \bar{n} is continuous up to 1 after which there occurs an abrupt change showing thereby the formation of 1:1 complex and absence of 1:2 complex.
- (ii) The solution employed being very dilute, the probability of existence of polynuclear species under experimental conditions is not expected to be high.

Approximate values of log K₁ were obtained by half-integral method. The accurate values obtained by pointwise calculations are reported in Table 1.

TABLE I
STABILITY CONSTANTS

Temp. : 90°C		$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$		
Sl. No.	Name of the ligand	pK_1^*	pK_2^*	$\log K_1$
1.	Phthalic acid	2.80	5.00	3.94
2.	3-chlorophthalic acid	2.28	4.99	3.91
3.	3-bromophthalic acid	2.43	4.99	3.77
4.	3-iodophthalic acid	2.48	4.62	3.49
5.	3-nitrophthalic acid	1.80	3.93	3.08
6.	4-nitrophthalic acid	1.98	3.98	2.93
7.	3:6-dichlorophthalic acid	1.40	3.40	2.99

* Ref. 7.

Complexation reaction :

In all cases the pH value when $\bar{n}=1$ is about 4. The pK_1 values of all ligands are less than 4, which indicates the dissociation of one carboxylate group before the complexation. In general, therefore, the complexation reaction can be represented as :

Validity of $\log K = a pK + b$ relation :

The values of $\log K_1$ are plotted against pK_2 values in Fig.1. It can be seen from this plot that

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K_1$ vs pK_2 .
Ligand numbers as given in Table I.

a single straight line passing through all the points cannot be drawn. However, two straight lines one for points corresponding to the vanadyl complexes of phthalic acid, 3-iodophthalic acid, 3-nitrophthalic acid and 4-nitrophthalic acid and another for 3-chlorophthalic acid, 3-bromophthalic acid and 3:6-dichlorophthalic acid can be drawn.

If the changes in the partial molar free energies of the metal-ligand and proton-ligand complexes exactly compensated each other, $\log K_1$ vs pK_2 plot should give a straight line with unit slope. When such a line passing through the phthalic acid complex was drawn, shown by dotted line, the point corresponding to the complex of 3:6-dichlorophthalic acid alone fell on the line whereas all the remaining points were either above or below the line. The points corresponding to the chelates of 3-iodophthalic acid, 3-nitrophthalic acid and 4-nitrophthalic acid were below and the remaining points were above the line.

The lower stability observed for the chelates of 3-iodophthalic acid and 3-nitrophthalic acid in comparison to their proton-ligand complex may be due to steric factors. The chelate of 4-nitrophthalic acid, however, should not exhibit steric hindrance. The lower stability of this complex can, therefore, be explained on the basis of $d\pi-p\pi$ interaction. If π -donation from the oxygen of the carboxylate group to the vanadium is responsible for the chelation, then the nitro group being a π -acceptor, should reduce the π -donation in the 4-nitro chelate though the effect would be too small at the oxygen donor. The "extra stabilization" observed from $\log K_1$ vs pK_2 relation for 3-chloro and 3-bromo chelates can be attributed to the fact that the lowering in stability due to the steric hindrance has been more than compensated by π -donation due to these groups.

Acknowledgement

The author wishes to express his sincere gratitude to Prof. D. D. Khanolkar, Senior Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry, and Dr. D. V. Jahagirdar, Reader, Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad for many fruitful discussions.

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